

AVIONICS INTEGRATION SUPPORT FACILITY DEVELOPMENTS ARE BECOMING BIG BUSINESS

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ABSTRACT

As the US Air Force (USAF) moves more heavily into computer controlled weapon systems, the requirement to support the attendant software is becoming a significant cost factor. The facilities developed to support this software are generically called Avionics Integration Support Facilities (AISFs). The facilities not only provide for changing the software but also provide for validating and verifying the completed programs. This paper will address AISF history in a summary form, AISF requirements in a general form, USAF attempts to reduce proliferation such as standardization and core concepts and an indication of where AISF developments are heading in the future.

AVIONICS INTEGRATION SUPPORT FACILITY HISTORY

It is difficult to tell when the first AISF was designed and built due to the genericness of the term and how one defines it. The Air Force has had complex analog computers in their weapon systems since the early F-101/F-102 days. These weapon systems were maintained in the field on mock-ups which in some ways, were similar to today's AISFs. However, AISF as we think of it today, implies support of embedded digital computer software. Embedded Computer System (ECS) in this sense means a digital computer and its attendant Operational Flight/Computer Program (OFP/OCP) which is dedicated to the weapon system in which it is a component. Utilizing this description of an ECS, the AISF history may be narrowed somewhat. Possibly the forerunners of today's large AISFs used for the support of ECS OFPs, was the F-111 AISF located at Sacramento Air Logistics Center (SM-ALC) CA. Later developments were the F-4 ARN-101 facility at Ogden Air Logistics Center (OO-ALC) UT; the E-3A support facility at Oklahoma Air Logistics Center (OC-ALC) OK; the F-15 AISF at Warner Robins Air Logistics Center (WR-ALC) GA; the Electronic Warfare AISF at WR-ALC; etc;etc.

Every weapon system with an ECS will require such a facility at the depot level. They are for the express purpose of maintaining software but have found many uses beyond this main purpose. Most of these facilities are multimillion dollar designs and when the total quantity is considered, a sizeable sum is involved which makes such facility development a big business. But as can readily be seen from the above synopsis, such developments can rapidly get out of hand. If one considers the

the total quantity of sophisticated weapon systems now entering the Air Force inventory, or destined to do so over the next five to ten years, you can see how the term proliferation may easily be applied. Therefore, the Air Force has become concerned over ways in which we can reduce this potential for proliferation of computer resources and reduce overall costs. But to understand how the problem arises, one must first have a comprehension of why these facilities are required.

AISF REQUIREMENTS

The philosophy underlying ECS is that in today's rapidly changing environment, it is necessary to have some means of rapidly changing weapon system capabilities. It is for this basic reason that computers are embedded in weapon systems to begin with. The software allows the system requirements to be changed rapidly, if needed, but is more for the inherent flexibility which can be designed into the system. The Air Force has found through experience that early in a development program, the ultimate scenarios in which the system will be used can only vaguely be defined. This is largely due to the advancement in technology offered by these systems. If one has never had the technology to use, it is difficult to envision its use in a theoretical battlefield. Therefore, after a system is brought into the inventory and fielded, the use to which it may be put is revised. The users, whether they be pilots or communication system operators in this environment, will begin to see new and better modes of operating a system after gaining experience. It then becomes apparent that the system is limited in its application due to constraints or bugs inherent in the original design. Then enhancements which remove limitations or enlarge the scope of operation of the system are designed into it. Also, as the users begin to push the system toward its limits, bugs built in during initial design and development begin to appear. These two factors, bugs not caught during initial testing and enhancements, lead to the requirement for having an AISF to revise the OFPs.

The first requirement of an AISF is to support the revision and enhancement of the OFP. This requirement by itself does not drive the complex AISFs that have been developed. Most of these facilities could satisfy the basic requirement with a fairly simple mini-computer driven software development facility.

Why then do we need multimillion dollar facilities? This comes from an additional requirement not readily obvious on the surface. The complexity of these systems; the extent of a simple system (i.e. a system used on multi-platforms which must interoperate); or the possible threat to personnel using the system dictates that a substantially tested and debugged OFP be used in flight or operational testing. This means that a sophisticated series of tests under simulated conditions must be conducted prior to operational testing and certification. This results in a net cost savings to the government. Since only debugged and simulation proven programs are flight tested, numerous flight tests and the attendant high cost of flight time plus range time can be avoided. The safety of flight problems are also lessened. In the case of multiple platforms, only large exercises such as Red Flag are available and can only be used to certify an already tested program.

The complexity of the simulations depend on the system being tested. For instance, at WR-ALC Engineering Division we have a range of simulation requirements. Table 1 shows a breakdown of various complexities of simulations.

TABLE 1

Simulation Scale	Types of Simulation Provided
Small	Platform Interfaces (Voltages, protocols, etc.), Platform movement (Nav System input/output sims), External environment (i.e. Laser input/output signals), Simple avionics simulations (Voltages, signals, protocols, etc.)
Medium	Platform Interfaces (Multiple/interoperating), Platform movements (Multiple snapshots in relation to each other), External environment (Jamming, emitters, targets, messages, etc.), Avionics (Multiple components, signals, protocols, etc.)
Large	Platform Interfaces (Multiple computer bus structures, weapons, etc.), Platform movement (Multiple degree of freedom, target and weapon relationships, etc.), External environment (Targets, weapons, etc.), avionics, (Radar, computers, bus structures, etc.)

The PAVE TACK Electro Optical Target Designator Set would be an example of a small simulation requirement. This pod contained system contains as the primary components a laser designator/ranger, an infrared detection set, and an embedded computer. In this facility we are simulating two environments. First, with just the embedded computer in the system, the PAVE TACK pod and platform, as well as the external environment are simulated. This simulation is useful after de-

bugging a program change on the software development facility and giving it the first operational test. Since there are a lot of electronic and mechanical devices within the pod which could be damaged if exposed to improper signals, it is necessary, initially, to simulate these items to prevent inadvertent damage. There is also a savings by not using the real equipment too often, thereby increasing the life of the components. Finally, if the pod equipment is down for maintenance and a quick turnaround test required, then we can continue testing with the pod off-line. The second mode of simulation is to put the ECS in the pod and use the production equipment to verify embedded computer operation. However, the platform and external environment still need to be simulated. This simulation, besides ensuring that the OFP is operating properly, performs a Validation and Verification (V&V) on the total system. When the software passes the test scenarios for the last stated simulation above, it is ready for flight test. The output from the flight test will be a certified program releasable to the using organizations. Since most of the testing and debugging is accomplished by the time the flight test is performed, any software problems found during flight test should be minimal. The tight schedules this late in the test cycle may mean that the software will be finally released with patches due to insufficient time to completely retest a reassembled program. Thus, we require the most error free program possible going into flight test to reduce patching to an absolute minimum. Flight testing is still required as the final step, for the following reasons: (1) The AISF is unable to physically move the pod, (2) Due to safety hazards, the laser cannot be operated in the lab, and (3) Laboratory distances do not provide necessary range for the infrared detection set operation.

The F-15 facility is at the other end of the spectrum as far as simulation is concerned. This facility is designed to support several OFPs associated with ECS in the aircraft. Because the F-15 Central Computer OFP controls the pilot interface with many of the aircraft avionics subsystems and the possibility of safety of flight problems, a much more complex simulation as well as more actual flight hardware is required to accomplish F-15 AISF ECS Support requirements.

The complexity of simulation stems from simulating the aircraft in flight, targets, weapon delivery and avionics. Test and pilot reports show that the aircraft simulation approximates real flight to extremely close tolerances. Besides the environmental simulation, any avionics system which depends on a dynamic flight environment is also simulated. The avionics simulations allow the facility to be operated when the actual hardware is inoperable or offline for other reasons. In some cases such as for weapons delivery, simulation is the only method of obtaining test data in the laboratory environment. Some of the same benefits as noted in the PAVE TACK description above are also obtainable with the F-15 AISF. Such things as protecting sensitive equipment from inadvertent voltage spikes, etc., until the program change is checked out are available through avi-

onics simulations. The F-15 facility gives another dimension to the simulation testing of the OFPs. Because a mock-up of the F-15 cockpit is included in the facility, a test pilot can fly the simulator prior to releasing an OFP change for flight test to ensure proper operation and to train him in new operations. The F-15 AIFS is also used as a V&V tool to certify programs for flight testing as well as a problem analysis tool. Again, since program release schedules become critical toward the end of V&V, it is anticipated that some patches may be required in the final programs.

Finally, there is a middle road to the ISF design efforts. Such a system simulation would be the Joint Tactical Information Distribution System (JTIDS). JTIDS is a different animal as to simulation requirements. Since we are talking about a digital communications system, the requirements are: to load the system with realistic data to verify specification requirements; to test special capabilities such as relative navigation and voice; to verify terminal to terminal interoperability; and finally to provide support to the Tactical Air Command (TAC) Joint Interoperability Tactical Command and Control System (JINTACCS) testing to certify programs for release.

JTIDS consists of a system of interoperable digital communications terminals. These terminals each contain an ECS with its attendant operational and built-in test (BIT) software. There may be problems with a fielded system which cannot be anticipated during initial testing. Thus, the laboratory must be capable of recreating a fielded configuration consisting of many terminals. Terminals are expensive so the number of active terminals in the lab will be kept to a minimum, therefore, the lab must be capable of simulating many terminals. This scenario must then be loaded with message traffic which approximates the load on the system when the failure or problem occurred. By recreating the fault conditions in the laboratory, the fault can be isolated to the software module generating the problem. A fix can then be designed and retested under simulated conditions. Other uses of the simulation capabilities approximate uses listed under the PAVE TACK and F-15 AIFS descriptions above.

It is instructive to realize that although an ISFs primary mission is to change and V&V software, that many other capabilities are inherent to the ISF designs. (Table 2) One of the major secondary uses of an ISF will be to support hardware and Automated Test Equipment (ATE) requirements. It is expected that through the life of a system, hardware problems will occur. These may be reliability/maintainability problems or just faulty design. Either way, the ISF, because of its simulation capability, can recreate failure modes for problem isolation. The ALCs also experience a lot of retest OK problems in ATE. This is when a fielded fault isolation program identifies a failed component which, when tested on Depot ATE, tests OK. The ISF will allow us to physically check for proper voltages and tolerances under operational

conditions to validate whether the problem is in fielded or depot level ATE and a fix determined. Along this same line of thought, the Built-in Test (Software) (BIT) and Built-in Test Equipment (Hardware) (BITE) embedded in the ECS may be revised as required. Another important use of an ISF, provided it can be designed and built early enough in a program schedule, is to provide Independent Validation and Verification (IV&V) of the system. This requires more regulatory support to ensure the System Program Office (SPO) properly budgets for it. Finally, these facilities for little extra cost provide ancillary services such as data reduction of operational test information, engineering support functions and configuration management support.

TABLE 2

Uses of an ISF

- Change and Debug Software
- Reassemble or Compile Programs
- Hardware Problem Identification
- Hardware Solution Testing
- Automated Test Equipment Retest OK Support
- BIT and BITE Support
- IV&V
- V&V
- DT&E/IOT&E (Development Test and Evaluation/Initial Operational Test and Evaluation)
- Data Reduction and Analysis
- Engineering Support
- Configuration Management Support

This completes a condensed look at ISF requirements. It can be seen that these facilities are complex and expensive. With almost every new system containing an ECS, the Air Force is beginning to see a problem of future proliferation of ISFs. I will next look at the steps the Air Force is taking to resolve this problem and reduce costs.

AIR FORCE ECS STANDARDIZATION

Several years ago the Air Force became concerned with the proliferation of computers and Higher Order Languages (HOL). It was during this time frame that the Air Force began the Avionics Planning Conferences on an annual basis. One of the main topics of discussion at the Planning Conferences is standardization of architectures and HOL.

Out of these conferences and other similar types of meetings have evolved several concepts on how to solve the proliferation problem.

First, a few thoughts on why proliferation exists, as it is such an obvious problem. As in all technology, when the Air Force first started buying systems with embedded computers, there was not sufficient expertise within the government to properly control the system acquisitions. Because of this, the procedure directions were vague or non-existent as to how to handle computer acquisitions.

The contractor has his own reasons for wanting to embed a particular type of computer. This, in turn, generally dictates the software support

requirements and hence, the facility. The contractor also will usually have developed some sort of simulation capability to check out his own software prior to Initial Operational Testing. This prior commitment to an ECS and attendant support equipment by the contractor forces the government to use the same, or compatible equipment if we are to take advantage of contractor developed software. Since software development or rehosting costs are high, use of contractor software and equipment designs are usually the most cost-effective route. Other costs not normally thought of, creep into the rehost effort. This comes from the fact that often when rehosting even a HOL program from one machine to another, small discrepancies in architecture implementation can cause the rehosted program to differ from the original. The rehost assembled or compiled program may differ from the original program, although both the host compiled operational program and the rehosted compiled program will accomplish the same mission. Thus, the rehost compiled program must be completely retested. Retesting entire OCPs is prohibitively expensive and this means the Air Force at a minimum has to duplicate or approximate the contractor's original software development facility. The government can opt to use upward compatible computers to modernize their facility for Life Cycle Cost (LCC) reductions but otherwise is severely limited in its options. The government is allowed some leeway in the simulation area if the contractor simulations are not adequate or are too costly due to the SPO not making the software deliverable under the initial contract. This will often force the government to do an organic simulation development effort due to lower LCC. Even though the government often has the option in these cases of hosting the simulations on computer facilities already in-house, these facilities generally already have full schedules and thus additional equipment is required.

The whole gist of the foregoing discussion is that standardization is easy to discuss but difficult to implement.

The Air Force Logistics Command (AFLC) is also investigating a concept which will allow centralizing ISFs. This concept sounds good on the surface, but let us take a closer look. In the previous section, I discussed three separate types of simulation requirements. While it might be argued that there is some similarity between an F-15 and a PAVE TACK environment, there is no similarity in either to the JTIDS requirement. When one considers other embedded computer system simulation requirements such as missiles, navigation systems, communications and radars, one realizes the futility of designing a generic simulator for all systems. However, there is a possibility of a generic simulator for all aircraft or for all missiles, etc., since the environments are similar. Thus, the core concept must be delegated to supporting a generic class of systems as far as simulation goes. Then there is the problem that when the load of both software change/debugging/assembly and simulation for multiple systems is considered, one can see that a mini-computer is not sufficient. Therefore, we are talking about multiple mainframes to

support the core concept on several different generic systems. There are other advantages to a core concept. One is that since all systems use the same basic computer and HOL, personnel can be reduced overall. Another is that even though multiple mainframes are required, there will probably be cost savings over using ISFs utilizing differing types of mini-computers. Disadvantages are that multiple systems on the same computer will prevent real time simulations without elaborate time sharing techniques or scheduling problems. With the time sharing techniques come very fast, large scale main frames in order to remain real-time or several simulations at one time with a resultant large cost increase. With the scheduling requirement come the problems of priority setting and infighting for scarce resources to meet individual system schedules.

One might argue that if the overall support of these systems is so complex, why not let the contractor support it? First, any new system has a AFM 26-1 study performed on it to determine the most cost effective and cost restrictive support philosophy. If it is determined that the contractor support is less costly, then contractor support is established. Contractors are not the least cost option most of the time, however. This is because of their higher overhead costs which are reflected into the contract engineer costs. Contractors also have a tendency to drop support of a system when it is determined that higher profits can be made by a different use of personnel and facility space. This is required contractor behavior if they are to remain competitive. One must realize the burden that such behavior puts on the government, however.

The initial decisions regarding organic versus contractor support options should be based on the mission essentiality and the anticipated life cycle costs (LCC) associated with the various support options. Mission essential systems are supported organically to ensure responsive peacetime and wartime support throughout the life of the option.

Support decisions regarding non-mission essential systems should be based on LCC considerations; however, the initial decisions must be tempered by the recognition that a decision to rely on contractor support can be difficult and costly to reverse at a later date because the contractors may be reluctant or unable to provide the government with the requisites (data, spares, training, etc.) of organic support. An early initial relatively low cost investment in the requisites of organic support can keep support options (contractor/organic) open and ensure that long-term support costs are held to a minimum. Any initial savings generated by going with contractor support must be weighed against the mission essentiality of the system and potential long-term support risks and costs.

The above discussions show that the Air Force is in the ISF support facility business. This is becoming a big business with big dollars being invested. Therefore, the Air Force has to be

concerned with how we can reduce these costs. Also, by the foregoing discussions, it should be seen that this is not an easy task.

FUTURE AISF DIRECTIONS

In the future, the government will tend to move toward a generic class of ISFs where as much commonality as possible will be carried from support of one system to the next. This type of philosophy requires a lot of ground work be accomplished first.

One thing that must happen is that procedures must be changed to support this philosophy. Along with the change must come a willingness to enforce it. The procedure changes that are required are for the SPO to be responsible for designing in reliability and maintainability during development. Also, the generic class of support equipment and HOL must be specified in the contract and Requests for Proposals (RFPs). This is required if we are to ever get control of the proliferation of support equipment. If the contractor knows that he must have a ECS which is supportable on a particular host machine with a particular HOL, then he will design that into his system. Once the system is designed to be supported on a particular generic host processor, then the Air Force can begin to reduce the proliferation of support.